

insects, none became infected.

Therefore, the interaction between ragged stunt virus and the brown

planthopper is categorized in the persistent group without transovarial passage. *W*

Rice sheath rot in Peru

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Sheath rot of rice has been reported for the first time in Peru. The disease has been found in Lambayeque state in the rice-growing areas of Chacupe and Chongoyape and in the "El Cienago" farm of the National University Pedro Ruiz Gallo. The disease affected the rice varieties Naylamp and Radin China and the pedigree line P866-F-204-1-1 from the cross IR930-31-10//F1 IR505/ Colombia 1.

The entire sheaths of the diseased plants were discolored gray to brown and the leaves yellowed. These symptoms of accelerated senescence were noticed from flowering to maturity. A brown mycelium was observed on the inner surface of the sheaths. Perithecium bodies were also found in the parenchymal tissue.

The characteristics of perithecia and ascospores suggest that the fungus belongs to the *Ophiobolus* genus. Its pathogenicity has not been tested, however. *W*

Transmission of rice grassy stunt by three biotypes of *Nilaparvata lugens*

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The ability of three biotypes of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* to transmit rice grassy stunt disease was studied through daily serial transmission to seedlings of Taichung Native 1 after acquisition feedings of 2 and 4 days. The insects of the three biotypes, differing in ability to attack rice varieties that carry different resistance genes, were supplied by the IRRI entomology department.

The test involved 4,690 insects and 27,374 inoculated seedlings.

The three biotypes did not differ significantly in their ability to transmit grassy stunt, as determined by percentage of active transmitters, latent period, retention period, number of infected seedlings per insect, and percentage of disease-transmitting days (see table). All showed transstadial passage.

The biological features, such as life span, nymphal stadia, number of molts, and molting intervals, did not differ significantly among the insects of the three biotypes used for the transmission study. *W*

Transmission of rice grassy stunt disease by three biotypes of *Nilaparvata lugens*, IRRI, 1977.

Biotype	Active transmitters (%)	Latent period (days)	Retention period (days)	Infected seedlings (no./insect)	Disease-transmitting days (%)
1	12.1	10.2	21.6	9.3	54.9
2	10.1	9.4	20.2	9.1	56.2
3	11.4	10.2	20.8	9.8	64.3
LSD (5%)	n.s. ^a	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

^a Not significant.

Transmission of rice ragged stunt by biotypes of *Nilaparvata lugens*

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The transmission of rice ragged stunt disease (see IRRN 5/77) by biotypes of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* was studied through daily serial transmission to seedlings of IR3839-1 after acquisition feedings of 2 and 4 days. The three biotypes used were supplied by the IRRI entomology department. They differed in ability to attack rice varieties that carry different resistance genes. A colony of brown planthoppers that had been reared on Taichung Native 1 in the greenhouse for several years but whose ability to attack rice varieties had not been determined was also included. The test involved 985 insects and 18,477

inoculated seedlings in three replicates.

The biotypes of the brown planthopper did not differ significantly in their ability to transmit ragged stunt, as determined by percentage of active transmitters, latent period, retention period, number of infected seedlings per insect, and percentage of disease-

transmitting days (see table). All showed transstadial passage.

The biological features, such as life span, nymphal stadia, and number of molts, did not differ significantly among the insects of different biotypes used for the transmission study. *W*

Transmission of rice ragged stunt disease by biotypes of brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* IRRI, 1977.

Biotype	Active transmitters (%)	Latent period (days)	Retention period (days)	Infected seedlings (no./insect)	Disease-transmitting days (%)
1	41.8	8.7	15.8	5.1	36.8
2	33.6	11.0	16.0	4.3	36.2
3	40.6	7.6	14.1	4.1	38.9
Undetermined	36.6	8.0	13.9	4.6	44.7
LSD (5%)	n.s. ^a	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.	n.s.

^a Not significant.